

Active Research: Document

[Analyze & Collaborate](#)

Facilitate Data Analysis

Analysis-ready datasets have been responsibly collected and reviewed so that analysis of the data yields clear, consistent, and error-free results to the greatest extent possible. Since raw data are often unstructured, data cleaning is part of the analysis process. Always keep a read-only copy of original raw data, and then document further processing and analysis.

- **[Tidy Data Principles](#)**: Each variable is in its own column, each observation in its own row, and each value in its own cell. This format facilitates data visualization and analysis using software languages.

Maintain Code Documentation

Establish documentation for code, scripts, and software. Version control is used to track changes to your files so you can collaborate with team members or go back and retrieve specific versions of your files later.

- ★ **Utilize [GitHub](#) to store, track, and collaborate on software projects**

GitHub is a web-based service for Git repositories (i.e., groups of tracked files). GitHub is good for code development; however, it is not a robust platform for sharing. Consider capturing an instance of your GitHub Repository in an established repository, e.g. Zenodo or Harvard Dataverse, to facilitate long-term preservation.

Document Data Analysis Protocols

Interpretation or analysis of data requires proper documentation. The type of analysis you perform depends on the type of data you're using and what the goal of your research project is. There are several strategies to enhance your analysis and fully capture your process:

- **Jupyter Notebook** is an interactive computing environment to create documents that include code, plots, text, images, and more. This streamlines analysis and provides a platform to rerun your work.
- **High-Performance Computing (HPC)** helps make your analysis more efficient and faster. HPC environments are connected to storage clusters where you can store the data being processed.
 - **[HMS Research Computing](#)** offers the O2 cluster, bioinformatics consultative services, and other assistance to support needs, analysis methods, documentation, and data transfer.
 - **[FAS Research Computing](#)** offers the Cannon Cluster, FASSE Cluster, consultative services, and other assistance to support needs, analysis methods, documentation, and data transfer.

- ★ [HMS Research Core Facilities](#) *provide specialized services, equipment, and staff for data analysis support*
HMS Research Core Facilities provide access to highly specialized services, equipment, and staff and can provide advice on documenting data analysis relating to the technology in their specific Core.

Document Image Management and Processing

Documenting the manipulation and analysis of images can help with processing and provide greater transparency of techniques. Additionally, sharing images in open formats (when possible) supports long-term access.

- **Recommended Open Formats:**
 - **Still images:** TIFF, JPEG 2000, PDF, PNG, GIF, BMP
 - **Moving images:** MOV, MPEG, AVI, MXF
- **[Image Management Resources:](#)**
 - **[OMERO](#):** Software for management, visualization, and analysis of microscope images
 - **Adobe Bridge:** Free software for locally organizing images
 - **ImageJ:** Free open-source, Java-based image processing and display tool
 - **Tropy:** Free, open-source software to organize and describe photographs of research materials